

Molecular structure, vibrational spectra (FT-IR and FT-Raman), NBO, Molecular orbital analysis and evaluation of microscopic NLO behaviour of (2E)-1-(4-bromophenyl)-3-(4-chlorophenyl) prop-2-en-1-one

K.Anitha^a, V.Balachandran^{b,*}, B.Narayana^c, B.Revathi^b, M.Karunanidhi^d

^aDepartment of Physics, Bharathidasan University Constituent College, Lalgudi, Tiruchirapalli 621 601, TamilNadu, India.

^bCentre for Research, Department of Physics, A A Government Arts College, Musiri, Tiruchirapalli , 621211, TamilNadu, India.

^cDepartment of Studies in Chemistry, Mangalore University, Mangalagangothri 574 199, India.

^d Department of Physics, Srimad Andavan Arts & Science College, Tiruchirapalli-620 005, India

Abstract

(2E)-1-(4-bromophenyl)-3-(4-chlorophenyl) prop-2-en-1-one (BP4CP) has been optimized by DFT (B3LYP) and LC-DFT (CAM-B3LYP) method at 6-31+G (d). A detailed vibrational spectral analysis was carried out and the assignments of the observed bands have been proposed on the basis of Potential energy distribution (PED). Molecular electrostatic potential (MEP) surface was plotted over the geometry to elucidate the reactivity of the molecule. NBO analysis has been performed in order to demonstrate charge transfer or conjugative interaction and delocalization of electron density within the molecule. HOMO–LUMO analysis has been done in order to determine the way the molecule interacts with other species. On the basis of vibrational analysis, other molecular properties such as ionization energy, electron affinity, chemical potential, global hardness and electrophilicity were also calculated. The electronic properties were determined by time-dependent LC-DFT approach. The microscopic nonlinear optical (NLO) behaviour of the BP4CP has been computed using LC-DFT method. From LC-DFT calculation results, the title molecule exhibits high microscopic NLO behaviour.